

Pre Teaching Questionnaire for Students

How old are you?

What year are you in?

What gender do you identify as?

Male / female / non binary / other

What is your ethnicity?

White – British

White – Irish

White - Any other White background

Mixed - White and Black Caribbean

Mixed - White and Black African

Mixed - White and Asian

Mixed - Any other mixed background

Asian or Asian British – Indian

Asian or Asian British – Pakistani

Asian or Asian British – Bangladeshi

Asian or Asian British - Any other Asian background

Black or Black British – Caribbean

Black or Black British – African

Black or Black British - Any other Black background

Other Ethnic Groups – Chinese

Other Ethnic Groups - Any other ethnic group

Not stated

Not known

Please enter your unique study ID number

1. Do you know what anaphylaxis is?

Yes

No

2. Can you explain what anaphylaxis is?

3. Would you know what to do if someone was experiencing anaphylaxis near you?

Don't know what to do at all

1

2

3

4

5

Know exactly what to do

11. How were the presentation slides?

Very poor 1 2 3 4 5 *Very good*

What was good about the teaching session today?

What could we do to improve the teaching session today?